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Deliverable Abstract

This report outlines the development of the **Social Computing Compass Researcher Self-Assessment Tool (KER 3)** aimed at advancing ethical AI design practices through cultural awareness and participatory methodologies. KER 3 is a gamified tool designed to address the social and cultural implications of AI development, specifically targeting software developers in academic and industrial settings. It builds upon principles of design justice and AI ethics to foster inclusivity, mitigate exploitation, and enhance democratic values in software design. The deliverable includes the link to KER 3.

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TERMINOLOGY

Terminology/Acronym	Definition
IDN	Interactive Design Narrative

TABLE OF UPDATES

Section	Update made
1.1	Minor updates to add a reference to the validation workshop as part of Use Case 4.
4.2	This section has undergone changes to update the storyboard and design of the game, which is now finished, validated, and accessible online. Only subsection 4.2.1 remains unchanged, while other parts are fully redrafted and restructured.

4.3	This is a new section documenting the validation workshop, which was part of Use Case 4 (full account in D 1.2, section 8.3)
5	The conclusion has been redrafted to include the necessary updates.
Entire document	General updates to grammar and syntax.

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Executive Summary

This report outlines the development of the **Social Computing Compass Researcher Self-Assessment Tool** (KER 3), part of the KT4D project aimed at advancing ethical AI design practices through cultural awareness and participatory methodologies. KER 3 is a gamified tool designed to address the social and cultural implications of AI development, specifically targeting software developers in academic and industrial settings. It builds upon principles of design justice and AI ethics to foster inclusivity, mitigate exploitation, and enhance democratic values in software design.

Objectives and Framework

The tool supports two primary project goals:

- **Establishing Guidelines:** It helps identify threats AI and big data pose to democracy by providing culturally sensitive decision-making frameworks.
- **Driving Democratic Technology:** It fosters ethically informed practices by integrating cultural dimensions into AI development.

Drawing from interdisciplinary approaches, KER 3 leverages narrative identity theory, critical digital humanities, and the emergent “Third Wave” of AI ethics. This innovative perspective shifts focus from prescriptive ethical norms to cultural complexities, positioning technological design as a profoundly social practice.

Methodology and Design Principles

The tool’s development was informed by findings from participatory workshops, which revealed significant gaps in traditional ethical approaches. Key insights included the ineffectiveness of checklist-based methods and the need for narrative-based interactive formats. The research team incorporated these lessons into a prototype that highlights cultural nuances, historical contexts, and the socio-technical challenges of AI systems.

The report also critiques conventional AI ethics frameworks for their inability to capture cultural depth. Instead, it proposes an **Interactive Design Narrative (IDN) game** that immerses users in ethically ambiguous scenarios. Through role-play and interactive storytelling, participants explore cultural biases, systemic constraints, and the unintended consequences of design choices.

Game Design and Scenarios

The game includes richly detailed simulations and decision-making frameworks, challenging players to navigate complex cultural and ethical dilemmas. Examples include:

- Addressing online bullying in diverse cultural contexts.

- Understanding linguistic subtleties and historical trauma in AI-supported platforms.

The game aims to:

- **Expose Cultural Blind Spots:** Highlight how technological decisions can marginalize communities.
- **Encourage Critical Reflection:** Foster nuanced thinking beyond standardized solutions.
- **Promote Cultural Awareness:** Sensitize developers to the diverse interpretations and impacts of AI systems.

Ethical Considerations

The game design ensures representation and creates a supportive learning environment. It emphasizes the importance of narrative agency, allowing players to critically assess their decisions and understand systemic limitations.

Social Computing Compass Researcher Self-Assessment Tool (KER 3) for Design Justice

1. Structural Framework and Theoretical Foundations

This report is based on KT4D's task 5.2, the main objective of which is to develop a comprehensive self-regulation tool that simultaneously addresses trustworthiness through top-down enforcement and bottom-up cultural transformation. This approach aims to support paradigmatic shifts in software development practices, ultimately fostering organisational structures and conceptual frameworks that prioritise inclusivity, mitigate potential exploitative processes, and enhance broader contextual understanding.

The Knowledge Technology for Democracy (KT4D) project addresses this complex challenge through the Social Computing Compass Self-Assessment Tool for Design Justice (KER 3). The tool's theoretical underpinnings are drawn from an interdisciplinary approach, integrating critical perspectives from digital humanities, Narrative Intelligence (Mateas and Sengers, 2003), narrative identity theory (McAdams & McLean, 2013), Design Justice Principles¹ (Costanza-Chock, 2020), and the emergent Third Wave of AI Ethics (Bolte & van Wynsberghe, 2024).

1.1 Tool Design and Methodological Approach

The Social Computing Compass Tool is conceptualised as an accessible, gamified resource specifically targeted at software developers operating within academic and industrial environments. Its core purpose is to stimulate profound self-reflective processes concerning the broader societal implications of AI system design, particularly in relation to civic and democratic participation.

To ensure comprehensive and nuanced development, the research team has systematically collected empirical insights into the values and subcultures characteristic of contemporary software development. The insights about the tool's design were primarily gathered during the initial workshop associated with Use Case 4, which took place in October 2023. The tool was validated during the last workshop of Use Case 4, which took place at Huawei Ireland Research Centre in Dublin in October 2025. Insights from the two workshops are documented in Deliverable 1.2, section 5.3 and Section 8.3 respectively.

¹ The Design Justice Principles are available here: <https://designjustice.org/read-the-principles>.

1.2 Project Objectives and Strategic Alignment

The tool directly contributes to two primary project objectives:

Objective 1: ESTABLISH GUIDELINES. Publish clear definitions and guidelines for where and how democracy is threatened by AI and big data. KER 3 empowers software developers to make granular, culturally sensitive decisions regarding their coding practices. By facilitating early-stage integration of these considerations, the tool operationalises the first project objective: establishing clear guidelines that elucidate how artificial intelligence and big data technologies potentially compromise democratic processes.

Objective 3: CREATE TECHNOLOGY INNOVATIONS ALIGNED TO DEMOCRATIC VALUES: Develop assessment tools and frameworks to drive/enable more ethically informed software development practices. The tool developed for KER 3 actively encourages the development of more holistic and genuinely human-centric innovation paradigms. This aligns with the third project objective of creating technological innovations that are fundamentally consonant with democratic values. By providing assessment frameworks, the tool enables more ethically informed software development practices.

1.3 Connections with the other WPs

The Social Computing Compass Tool is strategically positioned within a broader interdisciplinary research ecosystem, building upon multiple work packages and modules of the Social Risk Toolkit (KER1):

- From WP3, the tool incorporates critical insights into the cultural ramifications of AI and big data technologies.
- WP7 contributes sophisticated perspectives on ethical AI development practices, including participatory machine learning and algorithmic accountability.
- WP6 provides nuanced reflections on critical digital literacy, further enriching the tool's conceptual framework.

The tool's development is further informed by empirical findings from the initial Use Case 4 consultation, which will be explored in subsequent sections of this report (see Section 2.1 and 2.2).

By synthesising these diverse theoretical and practical perspectives, the Social Computing Compass Tool represents an interdisciplinary approach to fostering ethical awareness and cultural sensitivity in technological innovation.

1.4 A Digital Humanities Approach to AI Ethics

The project's initial conceptualisation proposed a straightforward checklist-based approach with interactive games primarily oriented towards citizen education. However, through an iterative co-creation process with target user groups, a more sophisticated methodology emerged. The research team discovered the potential of serious gaming as a transformative mechanism for fostering ethical software design, marking a significant paradigmatic shift in approach.

The decision to develop an Interactive Digital Narrative (IDN) game, rather than a conventional checklist, is fundamentally grounded in a critical digital humanities methodology that serves as the conceptual cornerstone of the entire project. This approach distinguishes the proposed tool from existing developer resources, offering a novel and nuanced intervention in the field of technological ethics.

Two core principles underpin the project's innovative approach:

- First, the research team emphasises the necessity of transcending traditional ethical frameworks to embrace a more comprehensive cultural perspective (see Section 3.2). This approach recognises the intricate socio-technical ecosystems generated by artificial intelligence. By applying humanistic research methodologies, this tool aims to enrich the current approach to human-centred AI, which is often informed by disciplines such as ethics and philosophy, by advocating for a more holistic approach drawn from the humanities and cultural studies.
- Second, the project develops a sophisticated understanding of narrative as a critical mechanism of human agency (see Section 3.3). Narrative is conceptualised not merely as a descriptive tool, but as a speculative instrument that enables more nuanced and critical engagement with complex technological and social dynamics. Specifically, the project explores narrative's potential to generate deeper awareness about the cultural implications of AI systems and to motivate developers' critical reflection.

In developing a serious IDN game, we aim to critically interrogate the intricate intersections between technological design, cultural complexity, and ethical awareness in artificial intelligence systems. The primary objective is to create an immersive pedagogical experience that moves beyond conventional approaches to technological ethics, challenging participants to engage with the nuanced social and cultural dimensions of AI development.

The game's fundamental design principles emerge from a critical recognition of the limitations inherent in current algorithmic approaches to social complexity (see Section 4). By

constructing a dynamic, interactive narrative environment, the project seeks to illuminate the profound epistemological challenges that arise when technological systems attempt to navigate cultural contexts. Specifically, the game is designed to demonstrate the fundamental inadequacies of standardised technological solutions when confronted with the multidimensional realities of human communication, historical trauma, and social interaction.

Central to the game's methodological approach is a commitment to several key pedagogical and ethical objectives: First, to expose the inherent limitations of algorithmic understanding by creating scenarios that reveal the depth and complexity of cultural communication. Second, to challenge simplistic technological solutions by presenting participants with nuanced, contextually rich interactive experiences that resist reductive interpretations. Third, to provide an immersive learning environment that cultivates critical reflection on the social implications of technological design.

2. Co-Creation: Use Case 4 and Methodological Refinement

2.1 Research Design and Initial Assumptions

The development of the Social Computing Compass Tool was deliberately grounded in an empirical approach, drawing directly from the first Use Case 4 workshop held in Dublin in October 2023 (for a detailed report, see D1.2). This methodological choice reflects a commitment to responsive, user-centred design that emerged from direct interaction with software development professionals.

The research team's initial hypotheses included the following key assumptions:

- Anticipated challenges in communicating the importance of professional computer ethics
- Presumed existence of widely recognised common tools among developers
- Expectation that ethical checklists would be a normative approach in software development
- Assumption of uniform difficulty in considering comprehensive user identity factors

2.2 Workshop Findings and Methodological Insights

The Use Case 4 workshop provided a critical platform for empirical validation of the project's initial hypotheses. The findings revealed a complex landscape of ethical considerations in technological design that challenged the research team's preliminary assumptions.

2.2.1 Key Workshop Revelations

Several pivotal insights emerged from the participatory workshop:

- Ethical Communication Challenges: Despite working with participants already predisposed to ethical considerations in artificial intelligence, the team identified significant obstacles in effectively communicating the importance of ethical software development. This insight led to a strategic reorientation, identifying tertiary educational institutions and human resources departments as primary target audiences for interventional approaches.
- Existing Tools and Dissemination Barriers: A surprising finding was the substantial disconnect between existing ethical AI tools and their intended user base. Despite the presence of numerous potentially valuable resources, workshop participants demonstrated minimal awareness of these tools, highlighting critical gaps in knowledge dissemination and technology transfer.
- Methodological Approach Refinement: Contrary to initial expectations, traditional methodological approaches such as checklist-based evaluations and competitive gaming models proved ineffective. Participants demonstrated a clear preference for more nuanced interventions, specifically narrative and collaborative game formats. The concept of 'red teaming' emerged as a particularly promising alternative approach to ethical reflection.
- Intersectionality and Cultural Complexity: The workshop revealed a nuanced landscape of identity considerations. Participants demonstrated remarkable comfort with intersectional perspectives—including gender, racial, and professional identities—while simultaneously expressing significant challenges in comprehending and integrating multicultural dimensions into software development processes.

2.2.2 Prototype Development and Conceptual Exploration

Workshop participants engaged in generative prototype development, producing two distinct conceptual approaches to ethical AI tool design (a more detailed report in D1.2):

CULTURaLi Prototype: The first group conceptualised an open-source multimodal tool analogous to Microsoft's Accessibility Tool for Vision. CULTURaLi was envisioned as a diagnostic instrument designed to highlight potentially discriminatory elements within large language models. The tool's primary objective focused on identifying and addressing culturally specific linguistic nuances, such as problematic idiomatic expressions and gendered language conventions.

A compelling example illustrated the tool's potential: the Irish idiomatic reference to 'Joe Bloggs' as an unidentified male, which lacks universal applicability. The proposed tool would suggest contextually appropriate alternatives, thereby enhancing linguistic and cultural accessibility.

ZombAI Prototype: The second group proposed a comprehensive suite of tools designed to address ethical considerations across different stages of software development:

- Pre-development phase: Bias detection and mitigation within datasets
- Development phase: An adaptive feedback mechanism using a traffic light system to evaluate ethical compliance
- Post-development phase: A collaborative game framework that evaluates ethical and cultural considerations through competitive team engagement

2.3 Methodological Refinement and Tool Development Considerations

Following comprehensive analysis of workshop insights, we developed the following critical reflections on tool development:

- The original checklist-based approach was definitively rejected in favour of more dynamic, interactive methodologies. While the workshop prototypes offered innovative perspectives, their technical complexities exceeded the project's current infrastructural capabilities.
- The emerging approach prioritises a non-competitive game model emphasising roleplay, imagination, and cultural exploration. An interactive fiction framework emerged as a promising paradigm, allowing participants to develop fictional products within simulated cultural contexts.
- The proposed tool will incorporate real-world examples identified as particularly challenging during workshop discussions, thereby grounding theoretical exploration in concrete, experiential learning.

By actively involving participants in a process of reflection and co-creation, our aim was to develop a tool that will hopefully help them better understand and address the complex ethical challenges of AI design. This approach allowed us to connect big-picture ideas about AI ethics with real-world solutions.

2.4 Key Design Characteristics

The development of the Social Computing Compass Tool was then based on the feedback we received. Additionally, it draws inspiration from innovative gamified approaches to ethical awareness. Two existing games that we thoroughly considered and learnt from are:

- The *Content Moderator SIM* serious game (available here: <https://samplereality.itch.io/content-moderator-sim>). This is a pioneering interactive experience that illuminates the profound psychological and societal implications of content

moderation practices and simulates the experience and ethical dilemmas faced by content moderators.

- The *Survival of the Best Fit* serious game (available here: <https://www.survivalofthebestfit.com/>). This Mozilla-funded educational game exposes AI bias in hiring algorithms and demonstrates how discrimination and unfair assumptions are baked into these tools in a way that make them go mostly undetected until large-scale damages are done and therefore evident.

In consideration of this, we identified three fundamental design principles that inform the tool's development:

Granularity: Granularity represents a commitment to verisimilitude and experiential authenticity. Just as the *Content Moderator SIM* meticulously reproduces the intricate tasks, workflow, and emotional landscape of content moderation, the Social Computing Compass Tool will provide a richly detailed simulation of software development contexts. This approach ensures that users engage with ethical and cultural considerations through a nuanced, contextually grounded experience that transcends abstract theoretical frameworks.

Openness: The tool's design prioritises complexity over simplistic solutions. Much like the *Survival of the Best Fit* game, our game should not provide answers or solutions but aims at highlighting complexity. It shows how to be critical and vigilant, which are skills needed in different contexts and circumstances. Rather than presenting prescriptive ethical guidelines, the intervention aims to cultivate critical thinking and adaptive vigilance. This approach recognises that ethical awareness is fundamentally a dynamic, contextual skill applicable across diverse professional and social domains. By emphasising critical reflection over normative prescription, the tool empowers users to develop sophisticated, transferable ethical reasoning capabilities.

Immersive experience: Immersion emerges as a critical pedagogical mechanism, offering a transformative alternative to traditional checklist-based ethical training. The tool will create an emotionally engaging, potentially unsettling experience that challenges users' preconceptions and induces deeper cognitive and affective engagement with complex ethical challenges. This approach recognises that meaningful learning occurs not through passive information consumption, but through active, emotionally resonant experiences.

3. Theoretical Framework for the Social Computing Compass Tool

3.1 Transcending Traditional AI Ethics: A Cultural Awareness Approach

The Social Computing Compass Tool fundamentally distinguishes itself from existing AI ethics resources by prioritising cultural awareness over universal human values. This approach reflects an understanding of technological design as an inherently contextual, culturally mediated practice.

Machine learning and AI-based predictive systems traditionally rely on identifying global regularities—consistent patterns that enable algorithmic generalisation. However, culture represents a complex domain that systematically defies such reductive approaches. Culture is fundamentally constituted by differences, nuances, and contextual specificities that resist standardisation (Hofstede, 2011; World Values Survey, 2023).

Culture is an elusive concept which is thoroughly discussed in Module G of the Social Risk Toolkit (Deliverable 6.1). In the context of the KT4D project, as stated in Module C of the Social Risk Toolkit (Deliverable 3.1), “culture is intended as a complex system of practices, knowledge, and norms that every person possesses and that is indispensable in the negotiation between the individual and its society.” This negotiation, which is ultimately what civic and democratic participation depends on, is often mediated and made possible by the knowledge technologies that we use. Far from being neutral intermediaries, these technologies are at the same time an expression of the very culture it produces them, a medium through which culture is performed and expressed, and a transformative – and often disruptive – force for cultural norms and values.

In order to come up with a workable definition of culture in the context of this project, we should then focus on what culture *does* rather than *is*. In this context, culture is intended as the set of beliefs, convictions, values that every person, as an individual and as part of a community, has and that determines their civic participation. For instance, a parent might be more invested in educational policies than the average citizen, and a religious parent might have different priorities and expectations compared to non-religious ones. Or, at the level of society, countries that strive for multiculturalism will have different values than countries following the melting-pot model of integration. This is what culture *does* to civic performance.

In relation to knowledge technologies, instead, culture is the filter through which people adopt, reject, and make sense of such technologies. This is not the only factor that determines technology use as, for instance, psychological and economic factors also matter. However, focusing on culture allows us to unpack the tension between the globalised, consumption-driven culture of media platforms and the local nature of community, and to switch the attention to the shared process of sense-making at the level of the community.

As an example of how culture shapes people’s understanding and use of technology, cell phones in Japan and South Korea “have shutter sounds with certain levels when their cameras are used. Such a sound cannot be made lower or removed” (Umeda 2008). This is to prevent people from being photographed without their consent and thus to protect the privacy, especially of young girls, who are often prey of unwanted attention. In Japan the phone manufacturers willingly adapted this so as to make the work of the Police easier; in South Korea, the government passed a law imposing that phones’ shutter sounds cannot be removed. In both cases the wellbeing of the community, its privacy and sense of security, is prioritized over the freedom of the phones’ users.

Another example is offered by the fast and positive reception of cryptocurrency in the Islamic world due to its compliance with Islamic banking that prohibits usury and speculation and thus any form of investments (Khan and Rabbani, 2022). In recent years, some Islamic scholars deemed cryptocurrencies halal and thus religiously permissible and are trying to prove that rules and regulations from sharia are fully compatible with digital blockchain technology. Religious beliefs are then what made the new technologies acceptable and indeed desirable.

The Social Computing Compass Tool’s primary objective is thus to sensitise software developers to these profound cultural dimensions of technological design. It seeks to illuminate how technical decisions and system requirements are interpreted and experienced differently across diverse cultural contexts, recognising that technological systems are not neutral infrastructures but active agents of cultural mediation.

Neglecting cultural specificities in technological design is not merely an aesthetic or academic concern, but a matter of significant political consequence. Technological systems that fail to respect cultural differences can profoundly disrupt democratic processes, marginalised communities, and perpetuate systemic inequities.

3.1.1 Cultural Awareness: A Critical Imperative

The urgency of cultural awareness in technological design is perhaps most starkly illustrated by the devastating case of Facebook's role in the Myanmar genocide (Amnesty International, 2022; Schissler, 2024). In 2017, social media algorithms facilitated the propagation of hate speech targeting the Rohingya people, contributing to a campaign of ethnic cleansing that resulted in thousands of deaths, displacements, and systematic human rights violations.

Mark Zuckerberg's 2018 U.S. Senate testimony candidly acknowledged the company's fundamental failure: “Hate speech is very language specific. It's hard to do it without people who speak the local language, and we need to ramp up our effort there dramatically” (Sydney Li and Jamie Williams, 2018). This admission underscores the critical importance of linguistic and cultural competence in content moderation and technological design.

Our serious game aims to prevent such tragic oversights by demonstrating how cultural insensitivity not only undermines democratic participation but also generates substantial economic and reputational risks for organisations. By presenting these consequences in an engaging, interactive format, we seek to cultivate cultural awareness among software developers and human resources professionals who might otherwise remain disengaged from such critical considerations.

3.1.2 The ‘Third Wave’ of AI Ethics

Our approach is theoretically grounded in what scholars have termed the ‘third wave’ of AI ethics (Bolte and van Wynsberghe, 2024), which transcends technical solutionism to analyse deeper systemic power structures. This paradigm represents a decisive shift from artifact-level technical interventions towards a more holistic understanding of technological systems.

The second wave of AI ethics predominantly focused on discrete technological solutions: curating inclusive datasets, refining algorithmic auditing techniques, and developing more equitable technical frameworks. In contrast, the third wave demands a more expansive analytical perspective that situates technological artifacts within their broader socio-technical context.

By adopting a critical digital humanities approach, we challenge developers to perceive their work not merely as code, but as complex cultural interventions with profound societal implications. Our serious game is designed to facilitate this transformative perspective, encouraging a more nuanced, contextually aware approach to technological design that recognises the fundamental role of cultural difference.

This approach aligns with recent scholarship (van Wynsberghe, 2021; Sætra, 2023; Stahl, 2022) that advocates for a structural turn in technology ethics – moving beyond narrow, technical fixes towards a more comprehensive understanding of how technologies interact with and potentially reshape social systems.

3.2 Immersiveness and narrative

3.2.1 Agency in interactive games

What is distinctive about serious games compared to other educational tools is their interactivity and immersiveness, which allow the player to engage with the material and questions at stake in a more engaged and active way. Such characteristics are usually understood as a consequence of the greater agency that serious games grant players when compared with other more static types of learning tools. In serious games – and in video games in general – people are often freer to follow different paths, choose their character, and write their own story. If, according to this formulation,

we equate interactivity and customization with agency, it is obvious that the greater the freedom accorded, the more effective in an agentic sense a serious game will be.

However, this equation and the definition of ‘agency’ on which it is predicated have been called into question for several reasons. Famously, in 1996, Lev Manovich challenged the assumption that the interactive mode made possible by computer and digital technologies empowered the user. Manovich saw interactivity as a form of manipulation that invites the user “to identify with somebody else's mental structure”. Instead, he posited, non-interactive media require an internal process of signification that is different for each individual and thus more empowering and non-manipulative. Although Manovich focussed on interactivity in digital art, his criticism ended up informing a wider debate on interactivity in games studies. His warning against mistaking engagement with real agency resonated with many scholars in the field (e.g. Fizek, 2022) and helped them problematize the concept of interactivity.

Furthermore, several studies in the last few years attempted to problematise the traditional liberal definition of agency as an individual quality and adopted a posthuman perspective that views agency as a collective and distributed quality (Harrell and Zhu, 2009; Keogh, 2018; Chia and Ruffino, 2022). Their concern is that interactivity in games might support individualistic and uncooperative behaviours and communicate an idea of agency as implying boundless personal freedom, and personal gratification. Not too dissimilar from Manovich’s concern, in this context traditional interactive games are accused of offering an ‘existential balm’ (Nguyen, 2020: 21) as they provide the illusion of control and reject ambiguities. As Chia and Ruffino (2022) argue, this situation calls for “a shift away from agency as a quality afforded in the closed circuit of game and player (Keogh, 2018) by building on understandings of play as assemblages co-constituted by players, platforms, and institutions (Taylor, 2009).” The invitation is thus for game studies scholars as well as game developers to “politicise agency in digital play” (Keogh, 2018), meaning to recognise the social and distributed nature of agency. In the context of fostering democratic processes, it seems perhaps obvious that this same rationale should apply.

There are several key points that our project borrows from these new perspectives of agency in games. First, we share the focus on the interplay between human and artificial agents and their shared agency, which is also the core issue addressed in our serious games. Second, we support the statement about the social and distributed nature of agency and of “the pervasive influence of culture on human intentions, beliefs, and actions” (Harrell and Zhu, 2009: 46). Finally, we share the belief that games can and should advance people’s understanding of how digital augmentation transforms agentic modalities (Bryant, 2021). To achieve this, ambiguities and contradictions should not be considered impediments to agency, but rather unavoidable aspects of the negotiating process on which civic and democratic participation relies.

3.2.2 Narrative as agency

Narratives have been long known to be an important contributor to empowerment processes (e.g., Alter 1993; Rappaport 1995). However, in games, the narrative component is often considered to be in tension with interactivity and, therefore, potentially limiting players' agency and freedom. This is because narrative, when understood as the framework imposed by game designers, sets the boundaries for users' exploration of the universe created within the game and, as such, should be kept to a minimum so as not to impede on the players' sense of freedom (Harrell and Zhu 2009: 44). Narrative and interactive elements are thus considered to serve opposite purposes, leading to what has been termed the "narrative paradox," according to which "the user's free will to navigate in, and interact with, a virtual environment is positioned orthogonally to a system's capacity to narratively structure the user's experience" (Harrell and Zhu, 2009: 44).

To reconcile such opposition that seems to be inherent to interactive games, it is useful to consider the concept of 'narrative agency'. This is defined as the "ability to position ourselves in relation to implicit narratives that steer our actions, self-understanding, and orientation to the future", as well as the capacity to "practice agential choice over which narratives we use and how we narrate our lives, relationships, and the world around us" (Meretoja, 2023: 296). The concept of narrative agency, although developed within the interdisciplinary field of narrative studies, has entered the discussion on narrative interactive games because it offers a solution to the "overly simplified understanding of agency [...] as free will of players" (Harrell and Zhu, 2009: 44) discussed in the previous section.

We choose to embrace the concepts of narrative agency and of narrative *as* agency in the design of our serious games because they are in line with our definition of 'critical digital literacy', which is also the final goal of our serious games. What the concept of narrative agency applied to the design of serious games offers us is twofold.

Firstly, it defines sensemaking as a narrative practice rooted in collective, cultural processes, which is in line with our understanding of culture as the filter through which people adopt, reject, and make sense of technologies, AI and big data included. Indeed, the goal of our game is for AI developers to question the cultural values and assumptions that shape users' interactions with AI, and to ultimately realise the link between culture, technology, and democratic participation. Our serious game thus intends for the user to become aware of the cultural and narrative process of sensemaking in a simulated environment that allows for critical self-reflection.

Secondly, the concept of narrative agency recognises narrative performance as a polyphonic process (Cunliffe and Coupland, 2011: 67) involving numerous contrasting opinions and points of views. This has to do with the fact that both narrative and agency are positional, as they depend on people's cultural values, personal and professional identities, access to knowledge, and more. This is a central proposition in the design of our serious game because within the same game we address

a variety of users or players. For us, to choose a specific target (e.g. entry level programmers versus senior tech company employees with managerial responsibilities) would not just mean to narrow the scope of our serious games, but to overlook the collective and often conflictual negotiations that designing AI and big data systems requires.

The power of narrative as a tool for negotiation – even in absence of full agreement – that leads to improved agency has been studied in relation to climate change. For instance, Vanderlinden et al. (2020), having engaged with several communities threatened by climate change in Greenland, India, Canada, and Kenya, observed that “a sensemaking approach may [...] contribute to keep the diversity of knowledges and interpretations alive yet somehow disciplined – in a way that may prevent the use of knowledge to impose power or vice versa” (12). To which they add that “stories and their deployment play a role in the ability of local communities to cope with changes. Agency and narratives are dynamically connected through sensemaking” (12).

Similar tensions and ambiguities animate the debate on AI ethics within the developers’ community on how to move from high-level principles to applicable and discreet solutions. Human and democratic-centred AI development principles, not unlike climate change, require a collective effort that starts with collective sensemaking.

4. Final Structure and Scenario for the Game

4.1 Design principles and Game’s Objectives

In the complex landscape of human-centred AI, our IDN game confronts the hidden tensions at the intersection of technology, culture, and power. We challenge the conventional understanding of technological design by revealing how well-intentioned interventions – from content moderation algorithms to participatory design frameworks – frequently fail when they lack a deep, nuanced understanding of cultural context and social dynamics.

Our interactive experience highlights the subtle yet powerful ways that technological platforms can inadvertently reproduce and amplify existing social tensions, demonstrating that what appears to be an objective technological solution is, in fact, deeply political and laden with cultural implications. Through a carefully crafted scenario, we illustrate how algorithmic recommendation systems can create insidious echo chambers, how privacy protections might paradoxically increase social vulnerability, and how the subtle nuances of contextual language can be completely obliterated by standardized moderation approaches.

The game is designed as a provocative learning mechanism that resists the comfort of clear-cut ethical solutions. Instead, we challenge players to recognise that cultural competence is not a checkbox to be ticked, but an ongoing, dynamic process of critical reflection, deep listening, and

genuine engagement. By making the failure of well-intentioned interventions a core learning mechanism, we expose the limitations of current approaches to technological design and social mediation.

4.2 Game’s Final Storyboard, and Interaction Flow

4.2.1 Game’s final design and link

We titled the Interactive Digital Narrative *Red Team Mission: The Incident at Pine Valley High* to clearly communicate the genre of the experience to players. “Red teaming” denotes a goal-oriented, adversarial exercise in which participants investigate an organisation’s systems, processes, and assumptions to identify weaknesses and mitigate potential harm. This type of exercise is commonly used within technology companies: drawing on a familiar professional practice was intended to lower the entry barrier for participants and facilitate engagement with the scenario.

Pine Valley High is the fictional secondary school for which the AI-supported system has been designed and deployed. While the name has an unmistakably North American tone, it was deliberately selected for its neutrality and lack of specific geographical markers, allowing the scenario to remain culturally recognisable without being anchored to a particular national context.

A further design decision was not to host the game directly on the KT4D website. Associating the experience too explicitly with the project’s focus on AI ethics and democracy risked signalling the intended “lesson” in advance and thereby reducing the experiential impact of the narrative. Instead, the game is presented as an artefact produced by a fictional technology company, *NexusDigital*, in order to preserve narrative credibility and avoid priming players’ interpretations.

For the same reason, the visual design is intentionally restrained and unbranded. The interface adopts a minimal, user-friendly structure combined with a retro-inspired aesthetic. This choice reinforces the impression of an internal corporate tool while maintaining accessibility and clarity.

The game is accessible here: nexusdigital-redmission.com.

Overall, the game is designed as an interactive digital narrative that places participants in a professional role of AI Safety expert, immersing them in a socio-technical crisis that cannot be resolved through technical reasoning alone. Its structure, components, and interaction flow are deliberately aligned with the project’s commitment to cultural awareness, narrative agency, and a third-wave approach to AI ethics.

4.2.2 Narrative Premise and Player Role

Players are introduced to a fictional scenario involving *NexusDigital*, a technology company whose AI-supported educational platform has been implicated in a serious cyberbullying incident at Pine Valley High School. The incident has generated public controversy, reputational damage, and legal risk for the company.

Participants assume the role of an *AI Safety Response Specialist* within a Red Team tasked with retrospectively analysing the incident. Rather than being asked to “fix” the system, players are instructed to identify the most robust legal and ethical defence strategy for the company by examining the broader socio-technical environment in which the harm occurred. This framing positions the player within institutional constraints and competing interests, reinforcing the distributed and negotiated nature of agency in real-world AI development.

4.2.3 Interface Structure and Core Components

The game unfolds through a web-based interactive fiction interface composed of several components:

- **Narrative Briefings**, which contextualise the unfolding events and establish the stakes of the investigation.
- **Document Exploration Interfaces**, where players review internal company materials such as design documents, moderation policies, system logs, and communications.
- **Testimonial and Expert Perspectives**, presenting partial, and at times conflicting, viewpoints from stakeholders including developers, school staff, legal advisors, and community representatives.

Progression through the game is linear in structure but interpretative in outcome: players are exposed to the same narrative materials, yet their understanding of causality and responsibility depends on how they connect cultural, organisational, and technical elements.

4.2.4 Scenario Development and Cultural Tension

As the narrative unfolds, players discover that the cyberbullying incident occurred during Pride Month and involved the widespread use of an orange lily symbol within the platform’s communication features by members of an LGBTQ+ student group. While many users adopted the symbol with inclusive or celebratory intentions, it carried historically traumatic connotations for a marginalised community within the specific cultural context of the school. For this community, the orange lily is associated with the memory of a massacre that resulted in widespread violence, displacement, and forced migration to the region in which Pine Valley High is located.

This cultural misunderstanding escalated into tensions among students and led to online verbal abuse and harassment. In the absence of contextual awareness, the platform’s automated content moderation system flagged and sanctioned several members of the marginalised group, who were accused of homophobia and subsequently had their accounts suspended.

Crucially, no single actor – neither the developers, the platform, nor the school administration – can be identified as solely responsible for the harm. Instead, the incident emerges from an accumulation of well-intentioned decisions made without sufficient awareness of local cultural histories and symbolic meanings. This design choice operationalises the project’s critique of technical solutionism by demonstrating how cultural trauma and collective memory often remain invisible to algorithmic systems and to the development processes that shape them.

4.2.5 Decision Point and Interpretative Closure

Once players consider that they have gathered sufficient information about the case and formed an interpretation of the causes underlying the incident, they are prompted to submit their final decision. This transition is introduced through the following message:

“When you have made your decision, click here to access the form through which to submit your feedback.”

Players are then required to select one of five defence strategies:

- **Design and Specification Processes** – Evidence suggests that responsibility lies in user interface design choices and feature specification decisions.
- **School Leadership** – Evidence suggests that responsibility lies in the school’s oversight obligations and failure to intervene appropriately.
- **Cultural Environment** – Evidence suggests that responsibility lies in the broader school culture and in contextual factors beyond the immediate control of the platform.
- **Technical Development** – Evidence suggests that responsibility lies in the robustness of safety algorithms and technical safeguards.
- **Data Control and Processing** – Evidence suggests that responsibility lies in the school’s data handling practices and in *NexusDigital*’s privacy protection measures.

Importantly, the game does not designate any option as definitively correct or incorrect. Instead, this final decision functions as a reflective mechanism that surfaces players’ implicit assumptions about responsibility, causality, and ethical prioritisation within AI systems. Each response begins by affirming the player’s choice (e.g. “You are correct...”) and explains how the selected strategy identifies a legitimate contributing issue. This is followed by a narrative reframing (“But there is

more to the story...”) that highlights additional factors overlooked by the chosen option and demonstrates how these intersected to produce the incident.

The absence of a single “right answer” reinforces the openness of the experience and resists the reduction of ethical reasoning to checklist-based compliance. Each response concludes with a real-world example illustrating how similar issues have manifested in non-fictional contexts, accompanied by links to academic and journalistic sources for further exploration. To encourage holistic understanding, links to the four alternative defence strategies are also provided at the end of each response, enabling players to revisit the decision space and engage more fully with the complexity of the scenario.

4.2.6 Experiential Learning Objectives

Through its storyboard and interaction flow, *Red Team Mission* achieves several interrelated objectives:

- It makes visible the limitations of purely technical or legalistic approaches to AI ethics.
- It foregrounds culture as an active force shaping how technological harm is produced and experienced.
- It situates ethical agency as collective, distributed, and constrained by organisational and social structures.
- It fosters narrative agency by allowing players to position themselves critically in relation to competing explanations and value frameworks.

Rather than prescribing ethical solutions, the game creates an experiential environment in which developers confront ambiguity, uncertainty, and cultural complexity as unavoidable dimensions of responsible AI design. In doing so, it operationalises the principles of the Social Computing Compass and exemplifies a third-wave AI ethics approach grounded in critical digital humanities.

4.3 Validation Workshop: Design-Relevant Findings

The near-final version of *Red Team Mission: The Incident at Pine Valley High* was validated during the third and final workshop of Use Case 4, held in October 2025 at the Huawei Ireland Research Centre in Dublin. The workshop served as an empirical checkpoint to assess whether the Interactive Digital Narrative effectively responds to developers’ needs, workflows, and ethical challenges. A full account of the workshop methodology, participant demographics, and results is provided in Deliverable 1.2, Section 8.3; the present section summarises only those findings most relevant to the game’s design and pedagogical objectives.

The validation exercise confirmed the core premise of the game: namely, that software developers recognise ethics as important in principle, yet experience significant uncertainty

regarding responsibility, operationalisation, and cultural scope in practice. Participant feedback demonstrated that the narrative scenario successfully exposed the limitations of purely technical or procedural approaches to ethical software development. In particular, the discussion surrounding the orange lily symbol revealed how culturally specific trauma and historical meaning can remain invisible to development teams, even when inclusive intentions and standard ethical safeguards are in place. This directly validated the game’s central design choice to foreground cultural unawareness as a source of harm that cannot be addressed through technical fixes alone.

From a pedagogical perspective, the workshop confirmed the effectiveness of the narrative, red-teaming approach. Participants reported good levels of engagement and realism. Moreover, the red team framing was explicitly identified as beneficial in reducing defensiveness and enabling more objective analysis, supporting the project’s emphasis on distributed and collective agency rather than individual blame.

The workshop also yielded concrete insights for refining the game’s structure and deployment. Participants noted that the time constraint used during the session created frustration rather than productive urgency, suggesting that longer engagement times—or the removal of strict time limits—would better support deep analysis, particularly outside facilitated workshop settings. We then decided to remove the time constraint entirely.

Crucially, the validation workshop confirmed that the tool is effective precisely because it does *not* offer definitive solutions. Participant questions about “what the answer should be” and whether awareness alone is sufficient reinforced the project’s theoretical position: the game is intended as an entry point for critical reflection, not as a comprehensive solution to software bias or cultural harm.

The validation exercise also generated practical insights regarding the future deployment of KER 3. In particular, it underscored dissemination as a central challenge, pointing to higher education curricula and industry professional development as the most strategic contexts for adoption. The game’s flexibility supports multiple usage scenarios, ranging from facilitated workshops to asynchronous self-study and hybrid formats, allowing it to be adapted to diverse learning environments and professional settings. These findings reinforce the importance of embedding the tool within existing institutional structures, supported by open access principles and community-building efforts to maximise reach and sustained engagement.

5. Conclusion

Through the development of *Red Team Mission: The Incident at Pine Valley High*, this deliverable has presented an alternative approach to ethical AI education that foregrounds cultural complexity,

narrative sensemaking, and the limits of purely technical solutions. Rather than prescribing definitive answers, the IDN game is designed to cultivate critical reflexivity, enabling developers to recognise how historical trauma, symbolic meaning, and institutional context shape the social impact of technological systems.

As demonstrated through the validation workshop (see Deliverable 1.2, Section 8.3), the game effectively engages developers in reflecting on ethical responsibility as a distributed and negotiated process. Participants' responses confirmed the value of the narrative, red-teaming approach in revealing cultural blind spots that remain invisible within conventional checklist-based or compliance-oriented frameworks. The strength of this gamified tool lies precisely in its capacity to make such blind spots experientially visible, without collapsing complexity into simplified prescriptions.

The design methodology underpinning KER 3 is informed by a commitment to ethical care, including attention to cultural representation, the avoidance of re-traumatisation, and the creation of a supportive learning environment. Beyond the IDN game itself, the work presented here contributes to a broader methodological framework for understanding AI systems as cultural interventions, offering a model for ethics education that centres human experience, collective sensemaking, and democratic sensitivity.

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